

5-SHO‘BA

TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH

IMPORTANCE OF MODERN MULTIMEDIA TOOLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION

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Abstract: This article discusses about the effective methods of using modern multimedia tools in the process of teaching English and their wide promotion.

Key words: multimedia, innovative technologies, electronic books, facilities.

Nowadays, learning and teaching foreign languages has become the demand of the time. The issue of teaching foreign languages has risen to the level of state policy, and we can see this in the actual implementation of the Decision No. 1875 on "Measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages". To ensure the effective implementation of the President's decision, English language rooms equipped with new innovative technologies were established in all schools starting from the 2013-2014 academic year.

The importance of listening to the pronunciation of English is incomparable. By listening to the pronunciation of a new word, the student acquires the ability to pronounce it correctly and consolidates it in his memory. Pronunciation exercises are the main part of the exercises in multimedia textbooks for primary grades.

Unit 1 All around me
Lesson 1 A - apricot, B - bee

1a Listen and sing.
Tinglang va kuylang.

2a Look, listen and point.
Rasmga qarang, tinglang va ko'rsating.

2b Play "I can say ...".
„Men ayta olaman ...“ o'yinini o'ynang.
e.g. A: a cat.
B: I can say "Meow".

3 Play "1, 2, 3-hop! 1, 2, 3-stop!"
„1, 2, 3-hop! 1, 2, 3-stop!“ o'yinini o'ynang.

6

4 Write the letters.
Harflarni yozing.

Aa

Bb

5a Look, count and match.
Qarang, sanang va mos rasm va raqamni belgilang.

5b Look, listen and repeat.
Rasmga qarang, tinglang va takrorlang.

7

Take the word "school" as an example.

4a Look, listen and guess

The image of a school is given in the multimedia tool, and if we bring the cursor to it, we will see that it is pronounced in the style of [skul].

You can repeat this process several times. Students will see new words and listen to the pronunciation and learn by perceiving through the picture. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the effectiveness of the teaching process.

To activate educational processes, various electronic books and interactive lesson maps have been created. It is proven that the educational processes are interesting through computer simulation models. As the process of learning English is made easier with computer tools, the demand for multimedia programs is increasing.

Multimedia tools ensure that the lesson is conducted in a live manner, and the possibility of revisiting the thematic virtual resources and repeatedly listening is expanded. The multimedia resources being created for English Language Arts provide language comprehension and the acquisition of new information through sight and hearing. We conduct classes using multimedia textbooks in rooms equipped with information communication equipment, which are very convenient for learning English.

This, in turn, leads to an increase in the effectiveness of the educational process. It is worth noting that, to achieve effectiveness, the teacher must, first of all, know how to use ICT perfectly, and familiarize students with the possibilities of ICT.

In conclusion, we can speed up the process of teaching English pronunciation by effectively using multimedia tools in English classes, and we can increase the quality of education by using its facilities.

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